

A Look at the Concept of Leisure

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Abstract

The number of approaches that try to explain human behavior in leisure time, which is assumed to correspond to about a quarter of the average human life, is undeniable. As it can be understood from the theoretical perspectives included in this study, the emergence of unexpected leisure time behaviors or the absence of expected behaviors are among the most important issues that should be emphasized, as well as the ideal leisure time behavior that people perform in their spare time. Undoubtedly, the concept associated with the emergence of leisure behavior on which many theoretical approaches are based is motivation. The types and degree of motivation can be associated with the reasons why a behavior did not occur, the reasons for the behavior to occur, the reasons for continuing the behavior, and the reasons for the termination of the behavior. However, trying to interpret leisure behavior only from the perspective of motivation can be seen as a big mistake. Therefore, concepts such as leisure opportunities, leisure time constraints, affective state, mood, competence, and autonomy perception, which interact with the concept of motivation, are among the most recommended concepts to be considered when trying to explain leisure behavior. Since leisure behavior has a structure that is affected by many psycho-social, cognitive, emotional, cultural and physiological factors, it is recommended to investigate and explain leisure behavior with a wider range of different theoretical perspectives.

Keywords: Leadership, Transformational Leadership, Construction, Construction Manager.

1. Introduction

Leisure Case

Leisure time is expressed as a period of time in which an individual can voluntarily participate in the skills to rest, have fun, improve himself or herself after fulfilling his/her work, family and social duties. Leisure time is the time left after the fulfillment of compulsory responsibilities and duties related to work and life, which the individual has the right to use freely on his or her own behalf. Motivation is defined as an energetic behavior directed towards a specific goal, the sum of efforts made to mobilize one or more people towards a specific goal, or the behavior of individuals with their own desires and wishes to achieve a specific goal. One of the characteristics of motivation is that it is personal. At the center of motivation is the person. People are distinguished not only by their abilities, but also by their motivation. Motivation is an individual phenomenon and differs from person to person. One of the main factors that determine the level of motivation is that people's needs are different. The individual's reaching a certain level of motivation through stimuli or motives plays an important role in the individual's participation in leisure time activities or overcoming the obstacles he encounters. In the individual's participation in leisure activities, internal factors come to the fore rather than external factors. Intrinsic motivation level is; Perception of leisure time is affected by factors such as the attitude developed by the individual towards leisure activities and the perception of barriers to participation in leisure activities.

Leisure Perception

Since leisure time itself contains "empty" in terms of words, it creates a negative/negative prejudice in us from the very beginning. While this prejudice has its roots in both tradition and religion, we cannot blame people for this understanding of the 'empty'. In our society, the 'empty' has always been the source of such prejudice. Discourses such as "these are empty jobs" are loaded with negative meaning because the work done is unnecessary and aimless. If a person realizes the time he describes as "empty work" and can reorganize it, it means that he has overcome many obstacles to success or has succeeded in paving the way for him to spend quality time.

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In this sense, the importance of time comes to the fore. A person can have more money, work harder and increase his money, go to the bank and get a loan, but not have more time. Perhaps the only irreversible thing in human life is time. For this reason, it is not correct to describe time as "wasting". Money is spent, but time is something that is not spent and is not 'wasted'. "Spending time", again in our language, has negative perceptions. It is also said to kill time. Whereas, killing time is defined with the word "killing" in the language of the speaker, perhaps in order to indicate it again, at a time when the person is actually himself. So, how should we use this extremely valuable thing, time, that will never come back?

We must first understand what time is, and more importantly, what it is not. This is what we try to explain in these units. In this sense, it is also extremely valuable to investigate what leisure time is and what it is not, how we are told, how we are taught how to 'spend', what was done in the past, what societies are doing today, what the governments wanted to be done, what the governments wanted to be done in the past.

On the other hand, if we think about it, everyone is actually given only 24 hours. In other words, Einstein, Imam Ghazali, the Prophets, or anyone else in the world did not have 25 hours. Here, of course, people intend to introduce the argument: "Terms". We do not have the same conditions as everyone else, it is possible to hear expressions such as. Although the conditions seem to be restrictive and restrictive, with the right time management, the number of things that the person can do and the quality of the things he wants to focus on, the way he bends should be examined well. We should never forget that we can turn our "leisure time" into "free time", and further, into "recreation", which we can describe as the time when people restructure themselves.

Transforming what is perceived as negative into positive is one of the biggest changes and leaps that a person can make in his life. According to Andy Warhol, "They say time changes everything, but actually, for change, you have to go and change." there is an emphasis on the active individual. Individuals who live actively and are aware of their time can create a different future for themselves by reorganizing their spare time.

In fact, it seems more appropriate to use "free time", preferably as a word, instead of free time. Free does not carry the meanings of the word "empty", it also includes freedom in the sense of "free" time. Of course, we will think of recreation as a lower circle and as a subset. Recreation has passed into our language today without being translated and unfortunately it has settled down. Recreation, in the broadest sense, can be thought of as self-renewal and restructuring.

2. Free Time

There is not a single word for "leisure" in general. We need to look at the etymology of the words "empty" and "time" separately. The point that will challenge us here is to understand the meanings in the sources we translate first, since we are translating from studies on the subject. Then we have to look at the etymology of the words that we think correspond to it in our own language, which shows that our job is not easy at all.

Although there is no single word for neither leisure nor leisure time in Turkish, the word "skhole" "σχολή (skholē)" in Ancient Greek means both leisure and leisure. Interestingly, it corresponds to the Latin word "schola". This is the word we know as school. Essentially, it also means a place where discussions are learned and free time is spent. At the same time, it is necessary to emphasize the relationship between education and leisure time.

Many dictionaries define free time as time independent of needs and work. Languages such as German and Spanish do not have a suitable word for leisure. It is used only as "free time". Because this definition seems to be simpler and more useful than others. Time is a structure that shapes possibilities and opportunities (Kelly and Godbey, 1992, 17).

In the etymological dictionary of the Turkish Language Institution, the word "empty" takes its share from the negative meaning we are trying to talk about, "1. With no person or anything inside, 2. Opposite of full, without an officer (job, task), vacant: vacant position. 3. Having no work to do, unemployed 4. mec. Meaningless 5th mec. Ignorant 6. mec. Useless, useless. 7. adv. rapier. Their meanings are listed as "uninformed".

Leisure can be measured, calculated, compared and trended in hours and minutes. “How much leisure?” The question of how much free time can be given an answer that seems self-explanatory. The leisure time of different social groups or individuals can be compared. They can determine their free time forecasts by keeping a diary or creating an agenda.

3. Neulinger's Leisure Paradigm: Its Subjective Definition

1. *Pure Leisure: This classification includes activities in which the individual participates freely for the sole purpose of feeling good (Neulinger, 1981, 31). It is completely internal motivation and freedom. External factors and consequences are not considered. For example, a forest trekking or a nature camp that a person attends for the sole purpose of feeling good is considered pure leisure. When the feeling of doing this activity in order to be a healthy individual in the future is added to these feelings, this activity is now evaluated under the second category, “leisure-work” (Leitner & Leitner, 2012, 7).*

2. *Leisure-Work: It includes activities in which internal and external rewards dominate and the person freely participates. There is a feeling of free time. Efficiency is satisfactory not only in itself, but also with the results obtained (Neulinger, 1981, 31). For example; Exercising can be given as an example to explain this category, as it not only contains internal feelings of well-being, but also improves physical fitness parameters and makes it healthier (external) (Leitner & Leitner, 2012, 7).*

3. *Leisure-Work: These are the types of activities in which there is free participation but the only source of motivation is external motivations. While doing any sports activity (jogging, pilates, fitness, etc.), aiming only to lose weight, be healthy and achieve other positive results of the activity (Leitner and Leitner, 2012, 7) or playing card games to earn money (without financial need) can be given as an example under this title (Neulinger, 1981, 32).*

All three categories above represent three different leisure experiences. In all three, the person is in the position of being the source of ideas for the situation that creates the feelings he experiences.

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One can terminate the leisure experience at any time without external pressure to continue (Neulinger, 1981, 32).

4. *Pure Work: Actions under pressure but with intrinsic motivation. In fact, there are feelings close to the satisfaction that free time brings, but it lacks the important component of freedom. The example of students who strive for their own development by doing research other than their homework can be evaluated under this heading (Neulinger, 1981, 32).*

5. *Work-Work: Actions that take place under pressure with both intrinsic and extrinsic motivation at the same time. The degree of satisfaction varies according to the ratio of internal and external earnings. But he has an awareness of the pressure that builds up, and however satisfying that might be, it's a non-leisure experience. An example of an academic who is satisfied with his financial gain and work can be evaluated under this heading (Neulinger, 1981, 32).*

6. *Pure Work: It does not take place with a reward in and of itself, but only with a profit from it. It is the opposite of pure leisure. The individual sees work as a job he has to do to continue his life and is not satisfied with waiting for a salary. These last three chapters are about non-leisure experiences (Neulinger, 1981, 32).*

Leisure time is the time that a person can use freely, except for sleeping, eating, drinking, meeting his essential needs, studying, working hours, traveling and having fun, and will use it in line with his own interests and abilities. The material elements of the society are developing rapidly and the development of the spiritual spheres is delayed. It is the cultural lag in the gap. The material aspect consists of raising the manpower needed for the industry in schools. Leisure education, which constitutes its spiritual aspect, is also delayed in schools.

4. Education

It is the process of changing the individual's ability, attitudes and positive values in the society he lives in. The purpose of education is far. Many items are mandatory. Volunteering is essential in

leisure time, individuality is important. It is a tool to join after school. Skills, understanding and assessment represent the program of education. Leisure represents as a means of use. Leisure education is the education of the individual to make use of his spare time intelligently. It is an education that helps the individual to evaluate his spare time wisely, to appropriate aesthetic and moral values, to express himself creatively and to get ideas. In terms of transferring and developing culture, making use of free time also has a great role.

5. Aim

In terms of social and personal welfare, the use of leisure time as personal development and social order improvement is leisure education. It is a useful opportunity to prepare for a good life and to develop one's personality. Evaluation of leisure time with a special action of the individual; interest, age, gender education, education, cultural and social status. Useless use of leisure time leads to deterioration of health, disruption of family life, decrease in professional efficiency, and destruction of civic consciousness. General Objectives of Leisure Education:

1. *To provide basic information to individuals,*
2. *Developing personality,*
3. *Preparation for life situations such as profession, social life.*

Leisure education includes enriching personal lives, creating interests, developing skills and philosophy of life. The individual should provide satisfaction and contribute to their personal development.

6. The Role of the Family

He teaches the family randomly and sporadically. Leisure activities mostly depend on the financial situation of the family. Participation in these actions is with parental authority. In urban areas, the individual can choose these activities more freely.

Leisure Education in Schools:

1. *Schools also prepare the individual to earn and live in life.*
2. *To arouse leisure interests, to motivate. It develops attitudes and values in this regard.*
3. *Some skills build the body. Provides mobility and motor coordination. Such as various games, athletics, sports and folk dances. Running, archery, tennis, volleyball, basketball etc. Some skills that schools will provide pleasure and satisfaction by contributing to the safety and survival of the individual. Like swimming. Others allow creative use of hands. Like painting, sculpture, woodwork. Some provide effective communication to the individual. Like literature, writing, reading.*
4. *To provide leisure facilities and services.*
5. *To develop and make use of physical resources for the use of leisure time. To prepare the individual for leisure leadership.*
6. *To cooperate with other community institutions in terms of responsibilities, interests, resources.*

Ways to Follow for Leisure Education

- a) *Some branches can be included in official curriculum programs. Physical education, language, graphic arts, social studies, handicrafts, housework... The approaches of different countries to leisure education are also the processing of social problems such as gambling, alcohol, delinquency, drug addiction.*
- b) *In the form of informal education: It is carried out outside of school hours and classroom studies. Suitable for flying, ski training, diving, etc. as...*
- c) *XXX-based leisure centers: The school is a center that meets the needs of the entire community. The programs are prepared to serve all ages and genders. It is open to service at any*

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time of the day. The community-centered school type is child-oriented. It helps him express himself. Benefiting from interests, program planning and individual freedom are essential.

d) Fulfilling community leisure opportunities provided by other institutions. Schools prepare the program; the responsibility belongs to the municipality.

e) Schools prepare personnel, train leaders, leadership has become a profession in developed countries. He is studying at the university level. Other leaders are trained for children, youth and adults.

- Emphasis is placed on schools mobilizing and coordinating all community resources, cooperating with institutions in planning, and conducting research on issues. And schools are built for leisure service.
- Apart from schools, religious institutions, the state, voluntary organizations and social welfare groups also have roles.
- Our schools have been given responsibilities for the purposes of our education. The aim was not realized because the curriculum was not given. Educational arm actions in our schools are also insufficient. Most of the educational branches cannot go out of school hours. It is not set as a separate lesson time. The facilities to realize these have not been prepared.
- There are no leaders to manage and train them outside of school hours. Fields such as physical education, painting, music and handicrafts that can be included in our schools are either absent or limited to two hours a week. Due to the large number of students and the limited number of students to be included in the activity, not all willing students can participate in this activity.
- A certain hour is not reserved for the educational branches. Most of them do not maintain a continuous operation.
- The afforestation arm can also be installed.

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- *The activities of the sports representation, painting and folklore branch are done outside of school hours.*
- *Most of the educational branches are established in accordance with the regulations and the studies are carried out only for show.*
- *Leisure education should be addressed within adults. Literacy and technical courses can be examples of this. These courses are more geared towards teaching a profession.*
- *Night schools, letter teaching, citizenship education, parent education, primary and secondary education courses, university courses in developed countries. There is also a training program for adults such as literature, art assessment, painting, sculptor, music, dance, sewing, photography. There are also programs that include business and current topics. If a diploma is obtained, it becomes adult education. Some programs are programmed and run by students. Some cooperate with faculty and administrative members. Associations, clubs, religious organizations, student unions play an active role in these studies.*

7. Leisure Activities in Turkey

It has features such as effortless, constructive, non-creative, watching, aimless wandering, resting. Leisure education directs individuals to constructive and effective actions.

- *Leisure activities are not organized. It aims to establish both voluntary and official organizations.*
- *The distinction between men and women is more evident in leisure areas.*
- *Working hours are getting shorter and free time is increasing. Schools should be considered as centers in this regard.*

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- *Actions to be presented to groups should be programmed.*
- *Cost should be planned.*
- *Support of voluntary organizations should be provided.*
- *Teachers should be taken to the leisure leaders course according to their abilities.*
- *All school staff should participate in the school-centered activity.*
- *The support of public institutions, professional associations, trade unions and religious organizations should be provided.*

Typologies of Leisure Actions

- *Creative Participation: Model making, composing, writing, creating.*
- *Productive Participation: Copying the model (Does his duty, plays basketball, sings, plays)*
- *Emotional Participation: Person who likes (Religions, visits the art exhibition...)*
- *Passive Participation: Boredom, relief, spectacle, hurt or harm. Extremes, crime, guilt, killing time, distraction from reality.*

Grouping of Actions

- *Physical: walking, travel, sports.*
- *Artistic: Dealing with various branches of fine arts.*
- *Practical Works: Handicrafts, handicrafts.*
- *Intellectual: Reading*
- *Community: Entertainment, visit.*

The student, who uses his spare time as a participant, develops a healthy, vigorous and solid personality. It provides integration, the individual who learns the folklore of different regions shares, adopts, loves the culture of those regions, and its spread ensures integration.

Churches have undertaken leisure education. By attracting active people to the church in this way, they ensure wider participation in church life. They prepare special programs for youth and community members. The aim is to attract new members to religious life. Camping, conference, picnic etc. Leisure rooms, sports halls, music festivals and art galleries of modern churches are criticized. He contributed to the provision of religious education to young people in Islam, the development of religious music, the dissemination and development of calligraphy and architectural decoration.

By opening summer camps, Kızılay provides music, folklore, painting, handicraft studies and making new friends. What should be done in the classroom should be done in the classroom, and what should be done in nature should be done in nature. In the absence of such education, an unfillable gap remains in human education. Besides school life, every young person should have a camp life. France envisaged a two-month summer camp and training.

Working areas for these activities should be created in the districts. Language and literature, fine arts, music, painting, decorative arts, concerts, folklore, opens exhibitions, encourages photography, spreads all branches of sports, organizes competitions, prepares presentations, broadcasts, provides aid, brings traveling doctors, opens a library. may be between

Interests in schools should be determined, and they should contribute to the development of sports such as athletics, swimming, wrestling, and diving that many people can participate in. Out-of-school youth should also be addressed. Summer camps should be organized. Parents should be trained in short-term courses.

8. Conclusion and Recommendations

In the twentieth century, many factors forced leisure education to change in terms of purpose and functionality. Developments in human rights, science and technology and changes in the socio-economic status of the society have led to an increase in expectations from education and forced the leisure education to change for the benefit of the individual by putting pressure on traditional education. Leisure education constitutes an important element in the changing understanding of education. At the same time, it directly or indirectly supports education outside of formal education. Leisure education has an important place in the functionality of the educational process (Torkildsen, 1992, 25). This educational process arises from the harmony between the intended and the experiences to be lived. However, necessary conditions must be created for this as well (Mosston and Ashworth, 2000, 1).

The educational process has many methods. For this, some favorable conditions must be met. So much so that the differences in individuals should be determined and a process should be established as a result of the evaluation of this. Some of them need to be defined, some are discovered by themselves, and some need to live by sampling (Kleindienst, 1978, 61).

However, while leisure education is classified in terms of quality and quantity, it is seen as the superior spiritual states of mind and body, and qualitative features such as thinking, being virtuous, love, excitement and wisdom are expressed in months, weeks and hours (Ağaoğlu, 2002, 16-20).

Although leisure education is a newly developing field in Turkey, there has been an increase in studies in this field in recent years. In this review, the literature and research findings in the field of leisure education have been scanned and classified, and the concept of "leisure education", which is gradually developing and accepted as an academic discipline, is discussed in many ways and it is aimed to contribute to the knowledge about the field.

In terms of social and personal welfare, the use of free time hours as personal development and social order improvement is the aim of leisure education. Leisure time is a good opportunity to prepare for a more prosperous life and to use it for personality development. People should choose

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activities that will make the most valuable and useful use of their free time. Undoubtedly, the evaluation of free time with a special activity depends on the individual's interest, age, gender, education, cultural and social status. The main goal of leisure education is how to evaluate leisure time, taking into account these characteristics of the individual (Tezcan, 1994, 76).

The main purpose is to learn to participate actively in the socio-cultural environment in which the individual lives and to share the values, rule and norm systems required by that environment with others and to interpret them correctly. While supporting the individual to realize the possible options and make the right choices, the individual develops the power to set goals and direct their own life, and in this way, they can contribute to the democratic society and make choices that are compatible with the society. The main purpose of leisure education is to raise versatile, flexible and harmonious people. At the same time, the development of cognitive abilities for common sense and logic is provided. For this reason, leisure education is a process that helps the individual to increase his harmony and lead a proud and beneficial life for himself and the society. Social movements are the starting point for determining the scope of leisure time education to be delivered to individuals, improving the quality of education, raising sufficient personnel trained in the leisure area, determining the amount of equipment and making investments (Türkoğlu, 1998, 92). These movements are decisive in the theoretical and practical fields of leisure education. Spending free time, which is very valuable for people, is important in terms of personal and social benefit. In addition, being able to integrate free time into life economically and socially has enabled this understanding to become widespread. Emphasizing the educational value and impact of knowledge is possible by transforming knowledge into attitude. The determining factor in its assimilation in this way is the place of knowledge in the life of the individual and whether it is an integral part of his real life. In other words, it is necessary not to be obliged to education, but to live education. Education should have a lively meaning for individuals who are integrated with life (Tezcan, 1994, 76).

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In this sense, attempting to educate a person without knowing what physical, mental, emotional, social and all other characteristics of the person we aim to gain behavior is, will cause negative use of time and opportunities (Büyükkaragöz, 1998, 99).

Leisure education is weak; those solid, constructive, creative institutions and traditions related to leisure time are not formed; In places where this culture is not competent, leisure time controls remain ordinary and within certain patterns. It is necessary to see free time as a way of exaltation. There, people walk by realizing themselves, and this is what needs to be learned (Erdemli, 2002, 50). There are opinions that how to evaluate free time does not require special learning, it occurs spontaneously, it is a free time, the individual can do what he wants. Such a thinking refers to the wrong evaluation and use of free time. Leisure education can traditionally be seen as teaching knowledge and skill. This training ensures the efficient use of free time programs and is included in non-formal education. Making use of leisure time constructively and intelligently is the goal of leisure education (Tezcan, 1994,76).

Leisure education is defined as education that provides individual satisfaction and enriches the individual, provides leisure opportunities, requires understanding the effect of leisure time on society, and aims to consider leisure behaviors (Graefe & Parker, 1987, 57).

Leisure education aims to make individuals or groups skilled in some special areas, to contribute to the development of society and to increase their quality of life. According to Neulinger (1981), leisure education should be related to leisure and should be associated with the individual, the individual's immediate environment and society at large. According to Peterson and Gunn (1984), leisure education should focus on acquiring and developing skills related to leisure time, improving behaviors and increasing knowledge (Graefe and Parker, 1987, 58). For this, individuals should be informed about what they like or what enriches their lives and adds to the richness of life, and their place in life should be determined accordingly (Means, 1973, 17).

Leisure time, which expresses free participation and has creative results, nourishes people with the right experiences and raises them as morally sound and virtuous people. According to Tolstoy,

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who supports this view, the basic principle of education should be freedom. In the ancient Greeks (VIII. and VI. centuries BC), it was aimed for the development of human beings in every way, that is, the development of the body and soul as a harmonic whole. In addition, according to the Japanese education philosophy, it was aimed to educate the people throughout life. Because education is a living phenomenon in every moment of life and it does not matter who or which institution gives it; The important thing is to educate the society. Otherwise, ineffective use of free time leads to deterioration of health, disruption of family life, decrease in professional efficiency and deterioration of civic consciousness (Tezcan, 1994, 76). The general aims of leisure education are gathered mainly in the following points:

- *To provide individuals with basic information,*
- *Developing personality,*
- *Preparation for professional and social life situations.*

It is obvious that there is a need for free time education in order to achieve these goals. According to many educators, leisure education can be achieved through the valuable use of free time through various courses or extra-curricular activities. Others see this education largely as a question of guidance in the form of the creation of interests and skills. However, there are differences of opinion on how to achieve this. In addition, leisure education includes a philosophy of life as well as enriching the life of the individual, revealing his interests, developing his skills. Leisure education should be equated with education for life and should be considered as a process that prepares people to use their time. In this process, the individual should provide personal satisfaction and contribute to all his personal development. Leisure education is aimed at giving them attitudes and values, interests and skills and developing them. The use of leisure time as a holistic satisfaction and creative purpose constitutes the purpose of leisure education (Tezcan, 1994, 76).

Woodburn (1978) created a guide study on leisure lessons. This author's strategy is to educate individuals by focusing on leisure education. It includes teachable elements, identifies leisure time

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with other subjects, requires learning with leisure experiences and focusing on leisure time based on these experiences (Graefe & Parker, 1987, 58).

Mundy has developed other criteria for implementing leisure education. These; The leisure education application model consists of awareness of life experiences, leisure preferences and leisure results (Graefe, 1987, 59). After studying these subjects, the next level is passed. These are goals, leisure experiences, decision making, and results. In other words, Mundy recommends step-by-step leisure training. This includes learning, activity and working processes and documents of specific experiences. If we want to show an exemplary process model (8-week free time education process);

Week 1: Definition and explanation of free time should be made. In addition, it should be tried to determine what individuals like and what they want to change in their free time by asking various questions.

Week 2: Individuals' needs and interests should be evaluated. In addition, the participants should be tried to understand their own free time as well as the roles they undertake in life.

3. Week: Conflicts in the participants should be tried to be identified and they should be eliminated.

Week 4: The preferences of the free time should be discussed and the subjects; What? When? With whom? How? And where? These preferences should be tried to be determined by taking answers to questions such as:

Week 5: Needs should be reviewed and objectives should be determined.

Week 6: Important connections with the society should be established; facilities, community literature and areas of interest should be presented.

Week 7: The decision-making process is experienced. How and why, they made decisions about free time should be discussed with the subjects and the issues should be discussed.

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Week 8: A focus and guiding action plan should be prepared. The education received should be transformed into a real leisure time behavior (Joperd 1994, 36-41).

Although these models are aimed at specific groups (e.g., school, communities, etc.), the majority of purposes, learning experiences are general, have aspects that can be applied to individuals and situations. Age, mental capacity group etc. Changes can be made according to the criteria. The most important application of leisure education is the applications of leisure service systems. Leisure education and the image of this aspect of life are the primary goals for the leisure area. The biggest responsibility here is our responsibility to influence our leisure lifestyles. Today, free time services are developing to be called and learned by phone. At the same time, leisure guidance services and guidance work can be developed. These cause people to recognize leisure resources and opportunities. While all these are being done, it is important to know whether people correctly understand leisure education as a concept and process, and to observe whether behavior and values are paid attention to in addition to physical activities. At the same time, it is necessary to know that besides the philosophical aspect of leisure education, it is the responsibility of the school system. It is also necessary to support leisure education as a course and concept (Graefe and Parker, 1987, 60).

It was built on the basis of the idea of using leisure time for human cognitive, affective and psychomotor development. According to Corijn (1987), he stated that he had reservations about evaluating the educational activities carried out in leisure time under the title of leisure education and that education actually uses leisure time to gain continuity. In this perspective, education for leisure turns into a form of "leisure for education" (Bosserman, 1976; cited in Corijn, 1987). From this point of view, he advocates the use of free time to support people in work, school and in different areas of life. Ancient Greek understanding emphasized that leisure time is the most important opportunity for the body and mind to develop together in harmony for both men and women (Torkildsen, 1992, 17). The point of view of Plato, one of the important philosophers of this period, is "leisure time", not as holiday time (loisir) reserved for entertainment and rest with its modern usage; It is that he sees it as a "leisure time" that means "school" (scholé) in ancient

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Greek and today, apart from the compulsory life efforts and production, that people devote to thinking and education and that does not produce instant utilitarian results (Rancire, 2000: cited in Gnen, 2005).). In this period, which is of great importance in the philosophy of education, leisure time is seen as a time to learn the details of the craft for the lower classes, while for the aristocratic layer, war skills, management skills, philosophy education as well as music for the beautiful soul, gymnastics for the beautiful body. It is a time period used for education (Ayta, 2012, 17). Gardner (1976) used the phrase “vocational education and leisure education are two concepts that go hand in hand”. A person who enjoys writing creative essays in his spare time can take a computer course in his spare time to improve his writing skills, while getting more pleasure from his other hobby, he can also use this skill in the business environment. Or, an individual who learns a foreign language in order to be able to communicate better on vacation can benefit himself by using this teaching at school (Bull et al. 2003, 270). Arslan (2013, 106) emphasized that life-long learning depends on adults' learning-based activities after school education is completed, depending on the individual's responsibilities and free time outside of working time. As can be understood from this determination, there is an important mutual relationship between lifelong learning and leisure time. Especially the course programs called adult education classes and evening classes reflect the “leisure for education” approach very well. According to 1998 data, 1.1 million people attended adult education courses in England (Bull et al. 2003, 270). In our country, it is possible to come across non-formal education practices in which many practices are made under local administrations and public education centers that meet the expectations of people to learn something in their spare time with classroom and workshop activities outside of schools. Edginton et al. (2004, 488) stated that it is possible to change both personal and leisure time attitudes of individuals outside of school with community and adult education, lifelong learning, semi-formal education practices and services provided by non-governmental organizations. Lowe (1985, 61) stated that adult education, which aims at the skills that people may need throughout their lives, can be evaluated under five categories as complementary education, vocational and technical education, health and welfare education, citizenship education, and self-satisfaction education (As cited in Arslan, 2013, p. 105).

Leisure education is a process to understand one's self, leisure time, the relationship of leisure time with one's own lifestyle and social production. The purpose and results of this process focus on improving people's quality of life. However, in order to understand leisure education, it is necessary to review the theory and practice of leisure education. In recent years, conceptual and theoretical models of leisure education have been developed. These; self-awareness, awareness of leisure time, behaviors, decision-making, social relationship, leisure activity skills, and political relationship. Therefore, leisure education is a long and ongoing phenomenon. In this process, there should be purpose, learning activities and strategies.

9. Resources

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